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Loss of immunosurveillance in TNBC.

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This paper describes cardinal changes in innate and adaptive immunity and natural killer cell function in TNBC. We previously described other aspects of immunodeficiency in TNBC including deficiency in IL2RG.

1 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the primary tumors of humans with TNBC.
2 We used the normal breast transcriptome as a reference transcriptome for differential expression analysis.

3 **Results**

4 Figure 1: ACADSB and ACSS3 were induced, as were SCOC and SDR16C5.

5 Figure 2: Steroid metabolism in TNBC: We observed activation of AKR1C1 and AKR1C3, DHRS24 and
6 DHRS7b, and Hsdb family genes including 17b8 and 11b2, as well as HSDL1.

7 **Self non-self recognition in TNBC**

8 Figure 3: LY6D was silenced, as was Ly96, and LY6E expression was significantly reduced.

9 Figure 4: Expression of AIF1 was also silenced.

10 Figure 5: LSP and EPSTI1 were repressed, but TSLP, SDF2 and less significantly, STAG3L4 were
11 activated.

12 **Antiviral signaling and the interferon system in the primary tumor in TNBC**

13 Figure 6: OASL and OAS2 expression was also reduced, and OAS1 reduction was weak but perceptible.

14 Figure 7: LCP1/2 reduction, with previously described IL2RG silencing.

15 Figure 8: This was coupled with loss soluble interferons IFNE and IFNG, as well as IFNB1.

16 Figure 9: IFNGR and IFNA6 reductions was more modest than observed with IFNK and IFNE.

17 Figure 10: IFNGR1 expression was modestly reduced, while IFNAR1 was weakly transcriptionally active.

18 Figure 11: IRF1, IRF4 and IRF8 expression was reduced or silenced, and IFNAR2 was not
19 transcriptionally active.

20 Figure 12: A putative mechanism of immunoevasion in TNBC through interferon silencing.

21 Figure 13: Immunoevasion featured IFIT2 and IFIT3 silencing.

22 Figure 14: Immunoevasion in TNBC through interferon silencing included IFI16, IFI44 and IFI44L, IFITM10
23 and IFIT5 as well as ISG20L2.

24 Figure 15: Innate immune: ADAR and IFIH1 were also silenced.

25 **Adaptive immunodeficiency in TNBC**

26 Figure 16: Expression of MR1 and MICB was not significantly different as compared to the normal breast,
27 but MICA was mildly reduced, as well as CD1a, CD1b, and CD1d.

28 Figure 17: Expression of Class II transcriptional activator CIITA was very modestly reduced but this was
not considered significant.

Figure 18: TAP2 was silenced, ERAP1 was repressed, but ERAP2 was not affected.

1 Figure 19: Adaptive immunodeficiency in TNBC is characterized by loss of class I transcriptional activator
2 NLRC5.

3 Figure 20: Adaptive immunodeficiency in TNBC was also characterized by virtual loss or significant
4 reduction in all classical MHC class I receptors of the HLA family whose expression was measured by
5 RNA-sequencing.

6 **Innate immune evasion in TNBC**

7 Figure 21: NLRC4 was silenced, while expression of NLRP7 and NLRP3 was significantly reduced.

8 Figure 22: Nucleic acid sensor RIG-I (DDx58) was repressed.

9 Figure 23: Virtually the entire TLR family was silenced or significantly transcriptionally repressed, including
10 TLR3, TLR1 and TLR2 and TLR8.

11 Figure 24: Expression of the DNA sensor absent in melanoma 2, AIM2, was completely lost in human
12 TNBC.

13 Figure 25: DNA sensor Zbp1 was repressed.

14 Figure 26: A network of immunoglobulin receptors silenced in triple negative breast cancer, which includes
15 Vsig4, LAIR1, and MILR1.

16 Figure 27: ILDR1 and LRIG1 were instead activated.

17 **Exhaustion in the primary tumor in TNBC.**

18 Figure 28: Themis2 was silenced while Batf was activated; Eomes expression was not significantly
19 altered.

20 Figure 29: TOX modulation in TNBC.

21 Figure 30: TOX modulation was accompanied by changes in CTLA4, near complete silencing of PD-L1, as
22 well as silencing or repression of CD274 (PD-1), TIGIT, HAVCR2 (Tim-3) and AHR.

23 Figure 31: BTLA expression was also significantly reduced, while LAG3 expression was not significantly
24 changed as compared to normal breast.

25 **The immunologic synapse in TNBC.**

26 Figure 32: CD84, CD72, and CD80 were significantly reduced.

27 Figure 33: Loss of immunosurveillance: This was characterized by silencing of cell surface receptors and
28 coreceptors that facilitate productive signaling at the immunologic synapse in T cells and in NK cells,
including CD4, CD300lg, CD163, CD226, CD86, CD14, CD180, CD3g, CD38, CD53, and CD2.

Figure 34: Reduced expression of natural killer activation marker NKG7.

Figure 35: Significant reduction in KIR3DL2 and KIR3DX1.

Figure 36: TNBC transcriptome was otherwise characterized by general loss of killer cell receptor
expression.

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Figure 37: Immunodeficiency in TNBC in humans was characterized by silencing of cell surface receptors and coreceptors that facilitate productive signaling at the immunologic synapse in T cells and in NK cells, including CD4, CD300lg, CD163, CD226, CD86, CD14, CD180, CD3g, CD38, CD53, and CD2.

Figure 38: Loss of immunosurveillance in humans with TNBC.

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Discussion

We provided here for the first time a systems biologic description of the immunologic landscape in triple negative breast cancer in humans (TNBC).

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Methods

We used R-based computational methods and RNA-sequencing (GSE185645) for this study.